

THE IMPACT OF AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP ON SMART ORGANIZATION: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF STRATEGIC AMBIDEXTERITY IN JORDAN TELECOM GROUP (ORANGE)

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Abstract

The study aims at identifying the concept of Authentic Leadership “AL” and its impact on the Smart Organization “SO” in Jordan Telecom Group (Orange) “JTG” and to examine the Mediating role of Strategic Ambidexterity “SAM”. The study population comprises all the members of the supervisory and directive management in JTG, which includes (737) members. The sample representing the population of (737) members is (250) members and in order to ensure population representation, (300) questionnaires were distributed by e-mail. Number of (292) questionnaires were retrieved. The Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) was used. The results of the study showed that there is a significant impact of Authentic Leadership with its dimensions on Smart Organization with its combined dimensions at level ($P \leq 0.05$) at JTG in Jordan; and the results showed also that there is a significant impact of Authentic Leadership with its dimensions on Smart Organization, through Strategic Ambidexterity at level ($P \leq 0.05$) at Jordan Telecom Group (Orange) in Jordan. Finally, and based on the results of the study, the researcher provides the following recommendations: JTG is recommended to provide professionals and specialists who conduct the needed proper assessment and analysis of the uncertainties’ effects on the company’s business; JTG is recommended to work intensively on the plans related to scheduling the tasks of its employees via implementing new flexible rotation plans among the employees.

Keywords: Authentic Leadership, Smart Organization, Strategic Ambidexterity, Jordan Telecom Group (orange).

1. INTRODUCTION

The current era (the era of the third millennium) may be the era that will witness an unprecedented momentum of rapid developments and changes, and there is no doubt that any business organization, irrespective of its field of work, is certainly exposed to these developments and changes. Al-Najjar (2015) states that there are multiple factors that cast a shadow over business organizations and force them to keep pace with the change in everything around them.

Technology is accelerating remarkably, the surrounding environment is witnessing fierce competition, and the age in which products were characterized by long life cycles is over. Al-Ukosh (2020) considers that organizations are originally smart entities because they are run by the minds that operate all the resources of the organization and therefore the organization that fails to extrapolate its environment and to sense changes in its external environment and that lacks the ability to adapt to these changes are expected to make many serious mistakes thus it is prone to collapse and to backwardness.

The SO aims at attaining the balance between what exists in terms of processes, resources and competencies and what it seizes in terms of opportunities in the surrounding environment. This is called Strategic Ambidexterity “SAM”, which is represented in exploiting the existing resources and potentials, exploring new opportunities and creating a state of balance between the two. There is no doubt that, the existence of a successful leadership at the head of a successful smart organization that moves the organization towards progress and excellence is a plus (Al-Bashqali & Sultan, 2021).

Accordingly, this study seeks to consider the impact of the AL with the whole positive leadership values it possesses on SO in light of the presence of SAM as a mediating variable in JTG taking into account that JTG is witnessing a frenzied competition in providing the latest products for its customers.

2. IMPORTANCE AND AIM OF THE STUDY

This study is considered the first of its kind-at the level of the Jordanian environment- that examined the impact of the AL on SO with SAM as a mediating variable so the researchers hope that this study will add value for future studies and will contribute in assisting the researchers with the needed theoretical background. Furthermore, as the population of the study, i.e., all the members of the supervisory and directive management, belongs to JTG in which the impact of AL on SO with SAM as a mediating variable will be tested and as JTG is dynamic and pioneering in using the state-of-the-art technologies and introducing the latest networks in its infrastructure, the researchers anticipate that the results of this study will contribute to give decision-makers in JTG a scientific evaluation of the level of impact of AL on SO with SAM as a mediating variable.

These results can be used to provide recommendations that highlight the importance of the studied variables (AL, SO, and SAM) for positively impacting the performance of JTG. This study aims at investigating and identifying the impact of AL on the SO in JTG in light of the presence of SAM as a mediating variable.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The modern administrations of business organizations have become interested recently in the SO and its dimensions represented by Understanding the Environment (UE), Continuous Learning (CL), Resources Mobilization (RM), and Finding Strategic Alternatives (FSA) especially in light of the great changes these organizations are undergoing and the intense competition they are exposed to in an environment characterized by strong turbulence and high dynamism. In view of the political and economic conditions experienced by the countries of the world in general and the countries of the Middle East in particular, the challenges that all Telecommunications companies, of course JTG is one of them, are facing have increased due to the strong competition, which increases JTG’s possibility to be exposed to threats related to the decrease in its market share due to the fierce competition in the Jordanian market. In the same context, Khaddam et al. (2020) indicate that the SO has a great ability to understand the surrounding environment with the means it possesses in terms of the use of information

technology, knowledge management, the Intelligence of its employees, and the development of its internal knowledge in creating new products, whether goods or services. Furlonger and Uzureau (2019) argue that business leaders bear a great burden in facing the challenges their organizations face from other organizations, and this pressures them to exchange ideas and collect information.

Van Droffelaar and Jacobs (2018) explain that it is very essential to tackle the transformation of the leadership style of the organizations to the post traditional styles of charismatic, servant, transformational and AL to face the aforementioned complexity and turbulent environment under the traditional leadership style. Thus, the need for AL, which is built on the positive leadership traits with high level of morals, honesty, authenticity and integrity in organizations under the conditions of fierce competition has become one of the attractive topics for study, taking into consideration that the conditions of competition in today's world are different due to the technological progress, the openness of markets and the convergence of tastes and preferences for the so-called "global customer".

Thus, it can be said that studying the need of SOs for AL has also become an urgent study issue; accordingly, the researchers could anticipate the need to investigate the impact of AL on SO through SAM as a mediating variable. In fact, achieving SAM is not easy as it entails conducting balance between exploitative and explorative activities taking into consideration that these activities require distinguished capabilities (Abu Zaid, 2019). Accordingly, the problem of the study can be formulated by the following main question: **"What is the impact of AL on SO through SAM as a mediating variable in JTG?"**

4. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- **The First Main Hypothesis:**

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of Authentic Leadership represented by (Self-Awareness, Balanced Processing, Internalized Moral and Ethical Perspectives and Relational Transparency) on Smart Organization through Strategic Ambidexterity at level ($P \leq 0.05$) at Jordan Telecom Group (Orange) in Jordan.

5. MODEL OF THE STUDY

Figure (1-1) indicates the study model, which includes its variables and the dimensions of each variable, in addition to the references that have been relied upon.

Figure No. (1-1) The model of the study

Source: developed by the researcher based on the following sources:

- **The independent variable:** The researcher has relied on the following references: (Otaghsara & Hamzehzadeh, 2017; Al-Mansi, 2020; Park & Seo, 2016; Iqbal et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Ciftci & Erkanli, 2020; Maximo et al., 2019; Ismail, 2015; Mahmoud, 2018; Okmen et al., 2018).
- **The dependent variable:** The researcher has relied on the following references: (Radi et al., 2018; Pharaon et al., 2015; Abboudi & Al-Maadidi, 2019; Hassan & Ibrahim, 2019; Khaddam et al., 2020; CĂLIN et al., 2015; Al-Sharafi, 2020; Alshrafi & Al Shobaki, 2020; Khalil & Hassan, 2019).
- **The mediating variable:** The researcher has relied on the following references: (Abu Zaid, 2019; Al-Ibrahimi, 2019; Alabadi et al., 2018; Lapersonne et al., 2015; Musigire et al., 2017; Dranev et al., 2020; Kar'awy, 2016; Voss & Voss, 2013; Popadiuk et al., 2018; Kosasih et al., 2020).

6. PREVIOUS STUDIES

The study of Khaddam et al. (2020) aims to study the direct impact of human resource management strategies in smart organizations in a group of pharmacies in Amman; the study of Wang et al. (2020), which was applied on a sample of (500) employees of a communications enterprise in China has concluded that: Authentic leadership significantly and negatively affects job insecurity; the study of Dranev et al. (2020) aims at studying the impact of organizational ambidexterity at organizational performance at energy and pharma companies; the study of Kosasih et al. (2020) aims to examine the role of change readiness in mediating the effects of ambidextrous organization and authentic followership on innovative

performance; the study of El-Sherbiny (2020) aims to identify the impact of ethical leadership on the organizational ambidexterity by applying to workers in commercial banks; while the study of Alshrafi and Al Shobaki (2020), which was applied on a sample of (45) administrative positions in Paltel has concluded that: there exists a strong relationship between the leadership of the organization and the realization of the characteristics of smart organization; the study of Mahmoud and Samuel (2020) aims to investigate the relation of authentic leadership practices with psychological capital and effort affective in teaching at Primary school teachers; the study of Al-Ukosh (2020) aims to identify the role of technology in building the smart organization; the study of Scheepers and Storm (2019) aims to investigate the influence of authentic leadership on ambidexterity; the study of Al-Akash (2018), which aims to identify the role of leadership in building the smart organization and its dimensions has concluded that there is a positive relation with statistical significance between leadership and constructing a smart organization at Arab hospitals.

7. AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP

1) Introduction to Authentic Leadership Theory:

AL is built on authenticity indicating a situation where individuals conduct in accordance with their values, beliefs, and human supreme nature; and, under various difficult pressures, persist with behaviors in line with self-values and beliefs (Otaghsara & Hamzehzadeh, 2017).

In this regard, Maximo et al. (2019) highlight that leaders should express their strong values of integrity, honesty and authenticity which all together comprise the set of distinguished societal values; in addition, leaders should be aware of the internal and external influences that impact subordinates as well as being aware of the processes of the organization. While Al-Mansi (2020) declares that Greece Philosophy used this concept to identify “know yourself to be authentic” thus authenticity refers to the personal experiences and behaviour according to the values that the leader believes in.

2) What is Authentic Leadership?

Operationally, this study defines Authentic Leadership as the basis of a positive leadership style, which focuses on the relationship between leaders and their subordinates. This relationship is characterized by mutual trust, transparency, respect and credibility. This supervisory relationship is based on the effective influence on the performance of the subordinates to achieve the desired goals. Laguna et al. (2019) explain that manifesting Authenticity by the leader is equivalent to transferring his /her attitudes and thoughts in his/her subordinates' acts; that is to say that the Authentic Leader inspires to the maximum his /her employees in exceeding what they are requested to achieve. Park and Seo (2016) consider AL as the process of clear compatibility between the leader's practical life and his/her characteristics; in addition, AL has a big influential role in the organizations' day-to-day activities. Wang et al. (2020) define AL as the balanced “Leader-employees” relationship which is based on mutual trust. Authentic Leaders are ready to express their true selves.

3) Dimensions of Authentic Leadership:

A. Self-Awareness:

Operationally, this study defines Self-Awareness (SA) as the leader being fully cognizant of his own strengths and weaknesses based on how he interacts with the others, and based on how his actions and words affect the subordinates. Iqbal et al. (2020) present the definition of SA as follows: it is where the leader, who is characterized with an inner-self-knowledge stability, is cognizant of his / her own strengths, weaknesses, values and beliefs. Mahmoud and Samuel (2020) state that SA is all that the Authentic Leader practices in terms of operations in order to understand and become aware of the perceptions of others about him/her in relation to his/her basic values, beliefs and ideas so that he/she is able to develop others and work with them in a team spirit.

B. Balanced Processing:

Operationally, this study defines Balanced Processing (BP) as the process related to manipulating and conducting an objective analysis of the raw data, characteristics and capabilities of the subordinates before taking a certain decision in light of this data with full awareness of the employees' views on the topics at hand. Ismail (2015) lists three main pillars for the definition of BP: analyzing objectively the information before decision-making, dealing with situations objectively without prejudice to one party at the expense of another and listening to different points of view.

C. Internalized Moral and Ethical Perspectives:

Operationally, this study defines Internalized Moral and Ethical Perspectives (IMEP) as the genuine conduct of the leader that reflects the leader's behavior according to his own beliefs and values in addition to his adherence to the society's standards and values without paying attention to the external influences. Mahmoud (2018) confirms that this dimension reflects the leader's reliance on the system of morals, values and beliefs as a motivation for him/her and a driver in difficult and turbulent times that require difficult decisions in the face of internal and external pressures.

D. Relational Transparency:

Operationally, this study defines Relational Transparency (RT) as the reliable relations that dominate the relations of the leader with the subordinates. This relationship is built on mutual trust, ability to work together and transparent information and ideas sharing in addition to honestly and objectively expressing feelings, emotions and opinions. Ciftci and Erkanli (2020) define RT as the leader's ability to construct or instill trust between him/her and his/her subordinates so as to share openly the information, thoughts and feelings and to provide supportive actions as well.

8. SMART ORGANIZATION

1) The Concept of Smart Organization

Radi et al. (2018) explain that SO as a contemporary concept is closely related to the research and development processes that distinguish one organization from another, as this tireless work includes creating a successful alignment and continuous adaptation between the organization and its external environment in which events are accelerated.

2) Definitions of Smart Organizations

Operationally, this study defines Smart Organization as the organization that deploys intelligence in all its day-to-day activities. In other words, it is the organization's inclusion of learning sharing within its administrative units and its ability to acquire, generate and disseminate knowledge.

The SO is defined in the form of a mathematical equation that combines intellectual capital, information technology and values as follows:

The $SO = \text{intellectual capital} + \text{information technology} + \text{values}$. From this definition, it is clear that the SO is based in its work on the availability of distinguished minds that it has from competent employees who are considered the most valuable assets in the organization due to their minds' abilities and skills in adapting to the environment of the organization that is changing continuously (Pharaon et al., 2015). Abboudi and Al-Maadidi (2019) introduce the concept of SO as follows: "It is the organization that promotes learning, and pays utmost attention and superior importance for collaboration, teamwork and information generation in decision-making".

3) Dimensions of Smart Organizations

1. Understanding the Environment

Operationally, this study states that Understanding the Environment refers to the smart organization's ability to analyze the internal and external environment surrounding it, i.e., the whole variables affecting the decision-making process in a way by which this analysis provides the organization with the deep understanding and full awareness of the complexity and dynamism of the uncertainties (environmental variables) and their root-causes in addition to the proper means to deal with them effectively.

Abboudi and Al-Maadidi (2019) define "UE" as the SO's perception and understanding of uncertainties, its adoption of the strategic perspective and its deep understanding of environmental analysis.

2. Continuous Learning

Operationally, this study defines Continuous Learning as follows: on the organizational level, Continuous Learning refers to the individuals' accumulative learning acquisition, learning dissemination, continuous training and development to enable the organization to face the ever-changing surrounding environment. This aims at generating higher value for the organization

which essentially provides the needed adequate resources and diagnoses improvements on an ongoing basis.

Khaddam et al. (2020) refer to the continuity of knowledge as the continuous process of individuals in their acquisition, generation and exchange of knowledge between them and the different organizational levels within the organization.

3. Resources Mobilization

Operationally, this study defines Resources Mobilization as the smart organization's actions in empowering, making better use of, maximizing and benefiting from its existing resources in its attempt to face the external troubled environment and to achieve sustainability. This entails exerting all the efforts and deploying different means by the organization to raise and allocate the resources so as to reach the objectives of the organization and face the dynamic complex environment.

Resources Mobilization includes three components:

a) Disciplined decision-making:

Alshrafi and Al Shobaki (2020) declare that this means adopting the proper processes, engaging the right people, and sharing the right information at the right time to help the leader make the suitable decisions.

b) Alignment of goals and empowerment:

This component includes empowering and encouraging employees to make decisions and participate in decision-making and the keenness to harmonize all regulations with the goals of the organization (Al-Sharafi, 2020).

c) Continuous flow of information:

Alshrafi and Al Shobaki (2020) stress on the necessity of creating the culture of the natural regular flow of information within the different administrative levels of the organization.

4. Finding Strategic Alternatives

Operationally, this study defines Finding Strategic Alternatives as the possible available options and scenarios that are developed by the organization to establish the basis and direction in which the resources can be optimally applied in a way to attain the organization's goals. Encouraging the innovative novel ideas yields to the provision of several alternatives that support the creation of high-quality decisions.

The SO that adopts strategic procedures in its daily business cannot be able to seize opportunities and create them without the presence of new alternatives and options and in dynamic and innovative ways in order to create opportunities (Khalil & Hassan, 2019).

9. STRATEGIC AMBIDEXTERITY

1) Introducing the Concept of Ambidexterity

Al-Ibrahimi (2019) indicates that Ambidexterity means creativity at work, meaning that a person innovates in his work without asking. SAM is one of the important topics that researchers are currently interested in. It can be said that organizations that are ambidextrous are exploiting their existing capabilities, along with great efforts in exploring potential opportunities for such competencies in organizations of similar ambidexterity. Although there is no specific agreement on the definition of SAM, it can be defined as the ability of the organization to compete, explore and exploit mature technologies and markets.

2) What is Ambidexterity?

Operationally, the researcher defines Strategic Ambidexterity as the skilled balance conducted by the adept organization between the exploitative activities and explorative activities. Dranev et al. (2020) argue that the Organizational Ambidexterity is determined by the balance that the organization creates between the exploitative and explorative activities. It focuses on the competition between these two. At the same time, the absence of this balance between these two swings of Organizational Ambidexterity will-for sure- impact negatively the organizational revenues growth. Popadiuk et al. (2018) introduce Ambidexterity as the ability of the organization to effectively manage the contradictions and tensions while dealing with exploration and exploitation. From one side, Ambidexterity can be defined as the organization's ability to manage contradictions and tensions, efficiency and effectiveness. From the other side, a second definition can be introduced which is the ability to explore and exploit at the same time. The definitions consider the firm managing two competing or contradicting goals and that's why the firm should have such ability.

3) Dimensions of Strategic Ambidexterity

- Exploiting Opportunities' Strategy:

Tsai and Ren (2019) define the exploitative strategy as the activities that the organization undertakes to improve and strengthen the current product market. Therefore, it is very important to carry out promotions of the current product (good and/or service) to strengthen and improve the relationships with customers.

- Exploring Opportunities' Strategy:

Al-Baghdadi and Al-Jobouri (2015) state that Exploring new opportunities means sensing, seizing and moving quickly towards the new opportunities and to be able to adapt to the volatile markets although this may be accompanied by potential risks. This yields to the emergence of new customers, new markets and new distribution channels. Musigire et al. (2017) indicate that the exploration strategy assists the organization in creating new products and entering new markets thus getting rid of rigidities.

10. THE THEORETICAL ROOTING AND RELATIONS BETWEEN VARIABLES

1) Relations between Authentic Leadership and Smart Organization

This current study is consistent with: the study of Qarmash and Al Najjar (2020), the study of Alshrafi and Al Shobaki (2020), the study of Al-Akash (2018), and the study of Salimi et al. (2019). Thus, the previous researches that have examined the relationship between Leadership and Smart Organization highlight that whenever the organization is concerned with exploiting the skills and capabilities of managers/leaders who often challenge the employees' ideas and insights, pressure them and push them to seek for solutions and not to intervene others' affairs, this in turn increases the chances of the organization switching to a smart organization. On the other hand, this finding of this current study differs with the study of Al-hawajreh (2018) who has affirmed the presence of moderate-level perceptions of top-level leaders of the Governmental Jordanian Universities of the capabilities of business intelligence. Furthermore, the results of the current study of Kulkarni et al. (2017) have shown that senior-level management championship has an indirect impact on developing the business intelligence of the organization via various ways.

2) Relations between Authentic Leadership and Strategic Ambidexterity

This current study is consistent with the study of Kosasih et al. (2020) which indicates that Authentic Followership impacts directly and significantly the ambidextrous organization. Also, this current study is consistent with the study conducted by El-Sherbiny (2020) which indicates- through statistical analysis- that there is a significant correlation between the dimensions of ethical leadership and organizational ambidexterity. Thus, the previous researches determine that Leadership is the most determinant of being ambidextrous. The researches stress on an important issue when these researchers link between the necessity for the Leadership to be tightly involved in fully understanding the business styles and behavior practices. This again highlights the direct impact of leadership on ambidexterity in business organizations. On the other hand, this current study is completely inconsistent with the study of Freij and Olsson (2014) which tried to measure the relationship between three different leadership styles, one of which is Authentic Leadership, and Organizational Ambidexterity. The results of this study indicated a negative impact or relationship between the leadership styles and the organizational ambidexterity. Additionally, this current study is not completely consistent with the results of the study of Scheepers and Storm (2019) which showed that there exists a significant small positive relationship between Authentic Leadership and Ambidexterity.

3) Relations between Smart Organization and Strategic Ambidexterity

This current study is consistent with the study of Sweis and Abdeen (2019); this research declares that the greater the interest in implementing business intelligence systems and taking appropriate decisions, this may lead to achieving the organizational ambidexterity. The researcher thinks that this is evident because ambidextrous organizations adopt simultaneously the strategies of exploitative and explorative and these require high levels of modern tools and well-established processes which are characterizing business intelligence.

11. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

1) Population of the Study

The study population comprises all the members of the supervisory and directive management in JTG which includes (737) members.

2) The Sample of the Study

The sample representing the population of (737) members is (250) members according to the sample table based on the permissible margin of error of (5%) (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). The researchers have used the proportional purposeful stratified sample. To ensure population representation, (300) questionnaires were distributed. A number of (292) questionnaires were retrieved accounting for (97.33%) of the total distributed questionnaires, which is a statistically acceptable percentage.

3) Unit of Sampling and Analysis

The sampling and analysis unit for this study consisted of the supervisory and directive management represented by (chief officers, directors, managers, team leaders and experts) whose number is (737) members in JTG.

12. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

1) Descriptive Statistics of the Model Variables: this part presents the descriptive measure of the sample's individuals towards the AL and SO. Table (1) shows the Means, Relative Importance and Ranks for AL's, SO's dimensions in addition to their sub-dimensions and SAM.

Table (1): Means, Relative Importance and Ranks for the variables of the study

#	Dimensions	Means	Relative Importance	Rank
1	Self-Awareness (SA)	5.970	High	2
2	Balanced Processing (BP)	6.010	High	1
3	Internalized Moral and Ethical Perspectives (IMEP)	5.949	High	3
4	Relational Transparency (RT)	5.868	High	4
General average for Authentic Leadership		5.949	High	
1	Understanding the Environment	5.179	High	4
2	Continuous Learning	5.747	High	1
3	Resources Mobilization	5.443	High	3
4	Finding Strategic Alternatives	5.466	High	2
General average for Smart Organization		5.459	High	
General average for Strategic Ambidexterity		5.836	High	

Table (1) indicates that the respondents' attitudes occupied a high level of importance for all variables. Table (1) shows that the independent variable, i.e., the Authentic Leadership came in the first place with a mean of (5.949), and this affirms that the independent variable has the greatest impact on the dependent variable in this study, i.e., in other words this is an evidence that the independent variable is the one with the greatest impact which can influence the dependent variable among all the variables of the study; all subdimensions of Authentic

Leadership were highly important: Balanced Processing (BP) has the first rank among the four dimensions of Authentic Leadership, and represents the highest rank with a mean of (6.010), and with a high relative importance, while Relational Transparency (RT) lies in the last rank among the four dimensions of Authentic Leadership with a mean of (5.868), and with high relative importance. The Mediating Variable, i.e., the Strategic Ambidexterity lies in the second rank with a mean of (5.836) and this is in line with the logical statistical literature which points out that the Mediating variable comes in the second rank in terms of its impact on the dependent variable. So, it can be stated that again the independent variable has a higher mean than the dependent variable. The Mediating Variable has the ability to strengthen the role of the Independent Variable. This is proved by looking at the value of the mean of the Mediating Variable which is less than the mean of the Independent Variable but higher than the mean of the Dependent Variable. Finally, the Dependent Variable, i.e., the Smart Organization came at the third rank with a mean of (5.459) and high relative importance. The Dependent Variable is the problem of the study so being in the lowest rank is in line with the normal statistical literature as it constitutes the phenomenon under study which entails a problem that needs investigation and solution; all subdimensions of Smart Organization were highly important: Continuous Learning (CL) has the first rank among the four dimensions of Smart Organization, and represents the highest rank with a mean of (5.747), and with a high relative importance, while Understanding the Environment (UE) lies in the last rank among the four dimensions of Smart Organization with a mean of (5.179), and with high relative importance.

2) Reliability of the Tool of the Study

The researchers measured the internal consistency between the paragraphs of each of the study variables depending on the Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α) where the result of the scale is statistically acceptable if the value of Cronbach's alpha is greater than (0.60) (Sekaran, 2006, 311). Table No. (2) shows that the results of Cronbach's alpha were higher than (90%) for all study variables.

Table (2) :Values of the internal consistency “Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient” for the study tool paragraphs

Variable	Paragraphs' Numbers	No. of Paragraphs	Reliability Coefficient (α)
Self-Awareness (SA)	1-5	5	0.942
Balanced Processing (BP)	6-10	5	0.948
Internalized Moral and Ethical Perspectives (IMEP)	11-15	5	0.931
Relational Transparency (RT)	16-20	5	0.932
Authentic Leadership (AL)	1-20	20	0.972
Understanding the Environment (UE)	21-24	4	0.925
Continuous Learning (CL)	25-28	4	0.943
Resources Mobilization (RM)	29-32	4	0.948
Finding Strategic Alternatives (FSA)	33-36	4	0.962
Smart Organization (SO)	21-36	16	0.969
Strategic Ambidexterity (SAM)	37-48	12	0.977

3) Multicollinearity Test

Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between independent (predictor) variables according to the study model, taking into account that the value of the correlation coefficient exceeding (0.80) is an indication of the existence of the multiple high linear correlation problem (Gujarati, 2004, 359). The results of testing multicollinearity between independent variables are explained by correlation matrix and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test as following:

Table (3): Correlation Matrix for Predictors Variables

Variables	SA	BP	IMEP	RT
SA	1.000			
BP	0.789**	1.000		
IMEP	0.727**	0.767**	1.000	
RT	0.679**	0.742**	0.770**	1.000

SA: Self-Awareness. BP: Balanced Processing. IMEP: Internalized Moral and Ethical Perspectives. RT: Relational Transparency.

Table (3) shows that the maximum value of correlation coefficient is between (Balanced Processing) and (Self-Awareness) which is (0.789). The rest of the values were less than (0.789), which means that there were no perfect relationships between the variables. As explained, in the statistical literature, the value of (0.80) and more is considered as an indicator of multicollinearity existence.

4) Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance

To confirm the previous result, the (VIF) for the absence of a multiple linear correlation in addition to Tolerance were calculated, and the results are as follows:

Table (4): Results of the multiple correlation test between independent variables

Variable	VIF	Tolerance
Self-Awareness (SA)	3.482	0.287
Balanced Processing (BP)	4.187	0.239
Internalized Moral and Ethical Perspectives (IMEP)	3.282	0.305
Relational Transparency (RT)	2.909	0.344

Table (4) shows that all VIF values were greater than (1) and less than (5). Also, the Tolerance value was confined between (0.1 and 1), which indicates that there is no problem of multiple linear correlation between the study variables; this gives evidence that there is no multicollinearity between independent variables (Gujarati, 2004).

5) Hypotheses Testing: this part of study explains hypotheses testing where Path Analysis applied by using Amos was used for testing the First Main Hypothesis.

• First Main Hypothesis H01:

H01: There is no significant impact of Authentic Leadership with its dimensions on Smart Organization, through Strategic Ambidexterity at level ($P \leq 0.05$) at Jordan Telecom

Group (Orange) in Jordan.

This hypothesis aimed at determining the mediating role of Strategic Ambidexterity on the relationship between Authentic Leadership with its dimensions and Smart Organization.

To test this First Main Hypothesis H01 that involves direct and indirect effects, Path Analysis using the (Amos) program supported by the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in order to verify the existence of support for a statistically significant effect at the level of significance ($P \leq 0.05$) for Authentic Leadership with its dimensions on Smart Organization by Strategic Ambidexterity. The results of this testing are as follows in table (5):

Table (5): Model Fit measures of the First Main Hypothesis H01

Abbreviation	Measure	Value	Accepted Range
CMIN	Chi ² calculated	18.216	
Degree of Freedom	DF	4	
CMIN/DF	Chi ² /df	4.554	Less than 5
GFI	Goodness of Fit	0.932	0.90-1.00
CFI	Comparative Fit Index	0.967	0.90-1.00
IFI	Incremental Fit Index	0.968	0.90-1.00
NFI	Normed Fit Index	0.962	0.90-1.00
RAMSEA	Root mean square error of approximation	0.075	Less than 0.10
Sig.	Significant value	0.000	Less than 0.05

Table (5) shows that all measures meet the accepted range of model fit; this gives the evidence that path analysis is relevant for the study model, and indicates the appropriate fit of the model with the data. The results of the statistical analysis in table (5) show that the value of Chi² is (Chi² = 18.216) with significance (Sig = 0.000), which is less than (0.05) which means that it is significant, and the value of the degree of freedom (df) is (df = 4), and the result of dividing Chi² on the degree of freedom equals (Chi² / df = 4.554) which is less than (5), thus this indicates the acceptance of the model.

The results show also that the Goodness of Fit Index is (GFI = 0.932) noting that the value is somewhat close to 1, and this indicates the adequacy of the goodness of fit of the quality in the model since as the value of GFI is closer to 1, the more appropriate the quality is.

Also, table (5) shows that the Comparative Fit Index equals (CFI = 0.967) which is also very close to 1, and this indicates the comparative alignment fit. The table (5) shows also that the Incremental Fit Index (IFI) is (IFI = 0.968) which is meeting the accepted range.

Normed Fit Index (NFI) as shown in table (5) is (NFI = 0.962) which is meeting the accepted range- as well. For RMSEA, i.e., Root Mean Square Error of Approximation “which must be close to 0”, its value according to table (5) also is (RMSEA = 0.075) noting that the value is close to zero which supports the goodness of model fit, and the above confirms the relevance of the model to the regression processes (Hair et al., 2018).

The direct and indirect effects of the Fourth Main Hypothesis H01 are shown in table (6) below.

Table (6): The direct and indirect effect coefficients for the Fourth Main Hypothesis

Variables				Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	Total Effect	
Authentic Leadership	→	Strategic Ambidexterity		0.759	...	0.759	
Strategic Ambidexterity	→	Smart Organization		0.391	...	0.391	
Authentic Leadership	→	Smart Organization		0.658	...	0.658	
Authentic Leadership	→	Strategic Ambidexterity	→	Smart Organization	...	0.297	0.955

Table (6) shows that the standard direct effect of Authentic Leadership on Strategic Ambidexterity is significant with value of (0.759), the standard direct effect of Strategic Ambidexterity on Smart Organization is significant with value of (0.391), and the standard direct effect of Authentic Leadership on Smart Organization through Strategic Ambidexterity is significant with value of (0.658) at the level of significance ($P \leq 0.05$). Also, the table (6) shows that the standard indirect effect of Authentic Leadership on the Smart Organization through Strategic Ambidexterity is (0.297) and this means that the Strategic Ambidexterity could explain (29.7%) of the impact of Authentic Leadership on Smart Organization. This refers to the mediating role of Strategic Ambidexterity on the relationship between Authentic Leadership and Smart Organization. Moreover, the total effect of (Authentic Leadership) through the mediating variable (Strategic Ambidexterity) equals (0.955). Moreover, we find that Strategic Ambidexterity is partially mediating the relationship between Authentic Leadership and Smart Organization. This indicates that we reject the fourth main null hypothesis and accept the alternative formula, which states that “**There is a significant impact of Authentic Leadership with its dimensions on Smart Organization, through Strategic Ambidexterity at level ($P \leq 0.05$) at Jordan Telecom Group (Orange) in Jordan**”.

Figure (1-1): Results of Path Analysis

13. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

There is a significant impact of Authentic Leadership with its dimensions on Smart Organization, through Strategic Ambidexterity at level ($P \leq 0.05$) at Jordan Telecom Group (Orange) in Jordan.

14. RECOMMENDATIONS

JTG is recommended to provide professionals and specialists who conduct the needed proper assessment and analysis of the uncertainties' effects on the company's business; JTG is advised to review its policies and plans related to the adopted methods of using and reallocating its human resources and their corresponding capabilities; and JTG might establish an organizational unit that is specialized in the projects' outputs revision so as to take the beneficial lessons of the performed projects for future similar plans and to gain the possible opportunities.

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